

SUPPLEMENTARY USER MANUAL

for downloading and running the source code

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1. Download links

Source code, annotation, and exemplary input data needed to run the statistical analysis described in the manuscript can be downloaded from the following links. **Before downloading these files manually, please follow the instructions below**, since some files will be downloaded by the method automatically.

Resource	Download Link
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Source Code (Files needed for execution of the method)	http://storage.googleapis.com/noncoding_analysis_hg19/src.zip
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Sample Files (Test files for running the method and learn about the file format)	http://storage.googleapis.com/noncoding_analysis_hg19/MutationTestFiles.zip
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Annotation (Large file that annotates the Hg19 genome, which will be automatically downloaded by the method during execution. No need to manually download this file for running the method)	http://storage.googleapis.com/noncoding_analysis_hg19/AnnotationFilesComplete.zip
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2. System requirements

We recommend running the analyses on a server environment or on a virtual machine in the cloud that fulfills the following minimum requirements:

- ≥ 20 cores/vCPUs
- ≥ 60 GB RAM
- ≥ 35 GB SSD hard drive (temporary for intermediate files during the execution)
- high-speed internet connection (for downloading genome annotation files)
- Windows or Unix based operating system
- Java version ≥ 8 (Java Development Kit 8 or higher)

3. Formatting your input files

Two types of files are required to run the statistical analysis: mutation files and a path file.

Mutation files are tab-delimited and contain all mutations and samples to include into the analysis (one file per cancer type). Mutations should be aligned to Hg19, since annotation files are formatted for Hg19. Mutation files should have the following column header (case-sensitive), other columns will be ignored.

Column Header	Annotation
Chromosome	chromosome of the mutation (1, ..., 22, X, Y)
Position	position of the mutation (Hg19)
Reference_Allele	reference allele (A, C, G, T)
Tumor_Seq_Allele	mutated allele (A, C, G, T)
Tumor_Sample_Barcode	unique identifier of the sample

Please do not use the “-” annotation for insertions and deletions, and annotate reference nucleotides before indel variants, i.e. format mutations as follows:

Reference_Allele	Tumor_Seq_Allele	Mutation Type
AGTT	A	deletions
A	AGTT	insertions
C	T	SNVs

The **path file** is a tab-delimited file with two columns and no file header. The first column lists the cancer type and the second column lists the path to the mutation file of the cancer type. If the mutation file is in the same folder as the path file, it is sufficient to provide the file name, otherwise please specify the full path to the mutation file. Even if you would only like to analyze a single cancer type, we recommend

including whole-genome sequencing data of as many cancer types as possible into this file, since the statistical model uses them for background calibration. If you do not have any additional mutation data than a single cancer type, you can use the exemplary mutation data provided with the method.

If possible, please use one of the following identifiers to name your cancer types in the first column: Biliary, Bladder, Brain, Breast, Cervix, Colorectal, Endometrium, Esophagus, Gastric, HeadNeck, Kidney, Leukemia, Liver, Lung, Lymphoma, Ovary, Pancreas, Pleura, Prostate, Sarcoma, Skin, Thyroid

The method uses cancer type-specific expression data for weighted multiple hypothesis correction. If your cancer type matches none of the cancer types above, the method will perform standard multiple hypothesis correction without using expression data.

To learn more about the file formats, you can download exemplary mutation and path files under the following download link: http://storage.googleapis.com/noncoding_analysis_hg19/MutationTestFiles.zip

4. Running the method

The following commands are for Unix-based systems (tested for Debian 10), but the Java-based method can be similarly compiled and run on a Windows-based system (tested for Windows Server 2016):

Step 1: If necessary, install `wget`, `unzip` and the Java Development Kit on your system:

```
sudo apt-get install wget
sudo apt install unzip
sudo apt install default-jdk
```

Enter “Y” when prompted to continue.

Step 2: Download and unzip the source code.

```
wget http://storage.googleapis.com/noncoding_analysis_hg19/src.zip
unzip src.zip
```

Step 3: Download and unzip the sample mutation files (unless you would like to use your own data).

```
wget http://storage.googleapis.com/noncoding_analysis_hg19/MutationTestFiles.zip
unzip MutationTestFiles.zip
```

Depending on your Internet connection, this might take a few minutes.

Step 4: Compile the Java files on your system.

```
cd src
javac -cp Jama-1.0.3.jar:commons-math3-3.6.1.jar *.java
```

If you run the method multiple times, you only need to perform this compilation step once.

Step 5: To run the method, change into the `src` folder (unless you did in the previous step).

```
cd src
```

From this folder, run the method with the following parameters:

```
java -Xmx55G -cp commons-math3-3.6.1.jar:Jama-1.0.3.jar:./ SignificanceNoncoding
<entity> <path file> <output folder> <annotation folder (optional)>
```

The parameters are as follows:

<entity> The entity for which mutational significance should be evaluate across the entire genome. The other cancer types in the path file will be used for background calibration. Please make sure that the entity is exactly spelled as in the first column of the file (case-sensitive).

<path file> Path to the path file (cf. format above) that contains the paths to all mutation files and annotates them by their cancer types.

<output folder> Empty folder in which result files will be written. If the folder does not exist, the method will generate this folder. Please make sure that this folder in on an SSD disk with sufficient space (cf. above), since intermediate files will be written to this folder and deleted after the method completed.

<annotation folder> If you manually downloaded and unzipped the annotation folder, you can specify the file path (optional). If you do not specify the path, the annotation folder will be downloaded by the method and deleted after completion. We only recommend using this option if you run the method multiple times.

-k You can add this flag if you would like to keep intermediate files after completion. By default large intermediate files will be deleted after completion. We only recommend using this option if you run the method multiple times.

For example, if you downloaded exemplary mutation files to your home directory, you can run the method for breast cancer on the exemplary data as follows.

```
java -Xmx55G -cp commons-math3-3.6.1.jar:Jama-1.0.3.jar:./ SignificanceNoncodingBreast ~/MutationTestFiles/MutationFiles.txt ~/SignificanceAnalysis/
```

The output will be written to the folder SignificanceAnalysis created in your home directory.

The method will take approx. 3 hours to completion. Please note that Java process will be terminated on Unix-based systems, if you close the terminal window or the ssh connection. To prevent this, you should add “nohup ... &” so that the method runs in the background and continues after you close the terminal.

```
nohup java -Xmx55G -cp commons-math3-3.6.1.jar:Jama-1.0.3.jar:./ SignificanceNoncodingBreast ~/MutationTestFiles/MutationFiles.txt ~/SignificanceAnalysis/ &
```

5. Output files

The output folder contains the results file FDR_Weighted_Combined_<entity>.txt after completion of the method (e.g. FDR_Weighted_Combined_Breast.txt for the example above). Unless you used the -k flag, this is the only file in your output folder. If the output folder contains other files, the method is still running in the background (typically ~3 hrs to completion).

The output file provides a continuous genome-wide signal of significance adjusted for multiple hypothesis testing (FDR). It further annotates the closest genes to significantly mutated regions (FDR<0.1). The file has the following four columns:

- 1) Chromosome
- 2) Genomic position (Hg19)
- 3) Significance value (false discovery rate, FDR)
- 4) Closest gene(s) for significantly mutated regions (FDR<0.1).

The gene with the highest expression is annotated by an asterisk (*).

6. Step-by-step instructions

If you do not regularly use a server or cloud environment, this section provides step-by-step instructions to run the method on a Virtual Machine in the Google Cloud. The method can be similarly run on any other Windows- or Unix-based server or cloud environment. We recommend using the Chrome browser to follow these steps.

Step 1: Sign in to the Google Cloud on your browser (console.cloud.google.com) with your google email account (sign up for free if you do not have a gmail account). If this is the first time that you sign into Google Cloud with this email address, you will need to agree to the terms and conditions to continue. In some regions a \$300 cloud credit may be available for first-time users (click on **Activate** on the top), which you can use for these analyses. Costs for one run are <\$10, so they should be covered by the credit.

Step 2: In the **Navigation menu** on the right and select VM instances. If this is the first time you use your account, it might take a few minutes for your account to get ready until you can create a Virtual machine (Compute Engine is getting ready...). In the field **Virtual Instances** click on the blue button **Create** to create a new Virtual machine (VM).

Step 3: You will need to create a VM with the following parameters: 20 vCPUs, 60GB memory, 100 GB, SSD persistent disk, and Debian / Linux10. In the dialog window, select in the field **Machine configuration** > **Machine type** > **Custom** (Select vCPU cores and memory). Select **Cores:** 20 vCPU and **Memory:** 60 GB.

Scroll down to the field **Boot disk** and click on **Change**.

Change **Boot disk type** to **SSD persistent disk** and **Size (GB)** to **100**. Leave **Operating system** as Debian and **Version**: Debian GNU/Linux10 (buster). Click on **Select** to confirm. Scroll down and click on **Create** to create the Virtual Machine. You will need to wait 1-5 minutes until your Virtual machine is running. A green tick next to your machine name indicates it is ready. to update the status.

Step 4: As soon as the instance has launched Click on **SSH** next to the instance to log into the command line of the instance through your browser. This might take a few minutes. Enter the following commands into the command line to run the method on the exemplary mutation files for breast cancer (cf. above for a detailed explanation).

```
sudo apt-get install wget
```

```
sudo apt install unzip
```

```
sudo apt install default-jdk
```

Enter "Y" when prompted to continue. This might take a few minutes.

```
wget http://storage.googleapis.com/noncoding_analysisgh19/src.zip
```

```
unzip src.zip
```

```
wget http://storage.googleapis.com/noncoding_analysisgh19/MutationTestFiles.zip
```

```
unzip MutationTestFiles.zip
```

```
cd src
```

```
javac -cp Jama-1.0.3.jar:commons-math3-3.6.1.jar *.java
```

```
nohup java -Xmx55G -cp commons-math3-3.6.1.jar:Jama-1.0.3.jar:./ SignificanceNoncodingBreast ~/MutationTestFiles/MutationFiles.txt ~/SignificanceAnalysis/ &
```

Hit enter to continue.

Step 5: The method will now run for ~3 hours in the background. It is now safe to close the ssh connection. To check the status of your method, log in again and type

```
ls ~/SignificanceAnalysis/
```

Upon completion, the only file in this folder will be FDR_Weighted_Combined_Breast.txt

Step 6: To download the output file FDR_Weighted_Combined_Breast.txt to your local computer, log into the Virtual machine using the ssh button on the right. In the ssh screen, click on **Settings** on the top right

 and select **Download File** from the menu. Type in the path of the output file and click on **Download** to continue. If you used exactly the file names from this example, the file should be located under the following path /home/<user_name>/SignificanceAnalysis/FDR_Weighted_Combined_Breast.txt where <user_name> is the name of your gmail account. If you are unsure about your username, type

```
ls ~/home/
```

to find out your user name. Depending on your internet connection, it might take a few minutes to download this file.

Step 7: Important to avoid any long-term costs!

After the analysis completed, click on the dot symbol next to your virtual machine to update the screen. This step is important to avoid any long-term costs from your analysis.